

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A TRANSVERSE RESEARCH TO IDENTIFY AND VIEWS OF
THE STUDENTS ABOUT DESCRIPTIVE (WRITTEN)
EXAMINATION ABOUT VARIOUS SPECIALTIES**¹Dr. Muhammad Zahid, ²Hafiz Muhammad Jawad, ³Dr. Mishal Imran¹RHC Dahranwala, Tehsil Chishtian, Bahawalnagar²Mayo Hospital Lahore³Rawalpindi Medical College**Abstract:**

Objective: The main purpose of this research work is to find out the views of the students about the examination at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.

Methodology: This transverse research work carried out at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from February to November 2017. A feedback Performa about examination developed to gather the opinions of the students who were attending the written examination for MD, MS or MTA during the research timeframe. Assessment of different variables carried out & an elaborate analysis performed.

Results: Performa of feedback filled for ninety-eight students. The rate of response was 68.36%. Generally, feedback from candidates about the written exam was positive. A large quantity of the candidates was happy with the method & preparations for this examination, but most of the candidates did not provide their views about some significant issues.

Conclusion: The collection of the views of the students about the written examination arrangement was an excellent effort to discover our shortcomings & identifications of the areas which require improvement. This research work concluded the positive opinions from the candidates about the overall administration of the process of examination.

Keywords: Feedback, Written Exam, Percent, Positive, Shortcomings, Overall, Candidates.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Muhammad Zahid,**

RHC Dahranwala,

Tehsil Chishtian, Bahawalnagar

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Zahid et al., A Transverse Research to Identify and Views of the Students about Descriptive (Written) Examination about Various Specialties., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(01).

INTRODUCTION:

The most important methods to improve a practice are audit & feedback, based on the concept that professional people will improve their practice when provided with the views of the subjects about their performance, displaying that their methods are not consistent with desirable aim [1]. Feedback is an administration tool used to review & revisit the effectiveness, value and correctness of that method under discussion. Assessment of any method or involvement through getting opinions defined as the method of evaluation to detect the shortcoming of a process so that those shortcomings may be rectified. Feedback leads to very vital modifications in the practices of professionalisms [2].

NICE (National Institute of Clinical Excellence) elaborates the system of feedback as “the organized, critical investigation of the worth of methods under discussion including the methods utilized for evaluations & calculations, the utilization of the resources & results of the overall systems” [3]. These audits accepted to evaluate the worth of process of examination are vital needs to the provision of excellent worth in the process of examination & provide chance to develop communication among different groups of this mechanism, enhance the grade of professional contentment & getting the main objectives proof of the standards but these audits pose a fear to the managers of the practice under discussion at the same time. Examination managers can take these assessments as the hindrances against their freedom or they may take these audits as dictation source in his areas of authority [4].

The outlines of the feedback of the students about the written exam from research works have utilized to

inform the officials of examination boards to modify and improve the system of examination [5]. The main purpose of this survey is to find out the feedback of the students about the examination process in that medical college.

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work carried out at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from February to November 2017. A special feedback Performa organized for the collection of the opinions from candidates appearing in written examination for MD, MS or MTA during the research timeframe. This work carried out to evaluate the effectiveness of the department of examination as overall preparations, language ease, invigilation & medical terms used in the exam, allocation of the time for the paper, invigilators attitude, opinions about the refreshments offered in examination centre & in the last were the comments of the students.

We gave Performa to ninety-eight students who were going to appear in the written exam. Those forms received back after the exam before the exit of the students from the examination hall. The analysis of the data carried out with the help of SPSS software. The descriptive analysis also performed & assessments of the variables are available in percentages & frequencies.

RESULTS:

Ninety-eight students got the forms of feedback. They were appearing in written exam of eighteen different specialities. The rate of the response from the students was 68.8%. The division of the students on the basis of speciality is available in Table – I.

Table – I: Various Students Levels Classification (MS, MDS, MCCM, MTA, Dip, M Phil) According to Specialty

Speciality	Number (98)	Percentage
Ophthalmology (Eyes)	3	3.06
General Surgery	5	5.10
ENT (Ear-Nose-Throat)	3	3.06
Accident & Emergency (Trauma)	8	8.16
Pediatric surgery (Children Surgery)	8	8.16
Orthopaedic surgery	9	9.18
Oral and maxillo-Facial surgery	5	5.10
Urology	2	2.04
Cardiology (Heart Related Diseases)	3	3.06
Nephrology	8	8.16
Pediatric Medicine	9	9.18
Gynae (Obstetrics)	11	11.22
Critical Care Medicine	4	4.08
Histopathology	5	5.10
Haematology (Blood Profiles)	2	2.04
Dermatology (Skin)	2	2.04
Gastroenterology	4	4.08
General Medicine	7	7.14

Generally, the feedback from the students about the process of examination was optimistic. Eighty-eight percent students were happy with the process & arrangements for the conduction of examination. There was a requirement of comments from students on seven topics as displayed in Table – II.

Table – II: Response of students on activities of Examination department (67)

Response Parameters		Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Not satisfactory	No comments
Overall Arrangement	No	18	31	10	4	4
	%	27.5	46.2	14.9	5.9	5.9
Question Paper	No	7	17	20	12	11
	%	10.4	25.3	29.9	17.9	16.4
Time Allocation	No	10	14	10	16	17
	%	15	20.9	14.9	23.8	25.4
Language	No	5	13	8	17	24
	%	7.4	19.4	12	25.3	35.8
Clinical Terminology	No	5	12	13	15	22
	%	7.4	17.9	19.4	22.3	32.8
Invigilation	No	7	17	9	11	23
	%	10.4	25.3	13.4	16.4	34.4
Refreshment	No	0	0	22	27	18
	%	0	0	32.8	40.3	26.8

About the complete arrangements from the department of examination, 46.2% candidates graded as good, 35.9% students graded from good to excellent in terms of paper, 35.9% candidates graded good to excellent for the allocation of the time, twenty-five percent students graded from good to excellent for medical terms utilized in the paper. About thirty-nine percent students provided positive remarks about the language of the paper, 49% showed their satisfaction about the system of invigilation & 40.3% students were not happy with the refreshments given at the time of examination. Astonishingly, 35% did not give their opinions about the language & invigilation. A large quantity of the students did not provide their view which was a matter of concern for the authorities.

DISCUSSION:

The feedback of the student is a vital identifier successful execution of the practice & also facilitate with the urge of betterment [6, 7]. There is significant proof about the efficiency of the audit together with for the change in the behaviour of the provider [8]. This work carried out to find the lacks and faults in the services arranged by the department of examination and their improvement in the future written exam. Positive feedback detects the right things about the practice under discussion. On the other hand, negative feedback detects hindrances in the achievements of desired goals [9]. There shows a clear disparity between feedback & criticism. Negative feedback is the help to correct the faults. Feedback is available in a manner of construction with the objective of encouraging betterment.

The rate of response in this research work was 68.38%. Other research works also concluded the same rate of response [10]. The cause of low response rate might be that candidates had not complete understanding about the detail of filling the Performa. But it was not compulsory for every student to give his opinion on every question. It was also concluded that as the examination was over, all the students tried to exit from the hall of examination without taking a reliable time to fill the forms of feedback appropriately. Students should get elaborate descriptive information about the form filling before the start of the forms. Poorman and Mastorovich described that “the most accurate time for the feedback is just after the completion of the exam by the students.

This research work displayed that a large quantity of the candidates was happy with the overall administration of the department of examination, the system of invigilation, language and medical terms. The students agreed that the paper was completely related to the field by fulfilling all the topic of the curriculum. This finding is consistent with the research work of Saed AM in which a large amount of the students showed his satisfaction about the arrangement of the examination [11]. About the perceptions of the students for paper, research concluded that more than sixty-five percent students agreed that question paper was well arranged according to the curriculum. Eighteen percent students were against the previous remarks. A research work Turkey also displayed the same outcomes about satisfaction regarding question paper [12].

Fifty percent students were showing their satisfaction about the allocation of time but 25% did not give their opinion on this. Vladimir discovered that

allocation of the time varies considerably across a setting of culture, demography, educational background and skills of students and their worth. The students who want more grades take much time in exam [13]. Sixty percent students showed no satisfaction about the language of the question paper. This area requires the enquiry. Results also discovered that more than 55% of students were not satisfied with the clinical terminology utilized in the question paper. Students take exam very seriously and improper conduct and behaviour of invigilators can be amended if it has an adverse impact on students.

This research work displayed that 44% students graded satisfactory to excellent about the process of invigilation while nineteen percent were not happy from invigilators and 35% did not give any response about his matter. James revealed that many students found it challenging in a secure condition [14]. The alterations in the refreshments are an accounted trend. This research work concluded that more than forty percent students were not happy with the refreshments & 27% did not give a response about this matter. An investigation is in need for the improvement of the quality of refreshments.

CONCLUSION:

This was an excellent attempt for the detection of our shortcomings & identification of the areas which require improvement. Compulsory feedback from students, examiners and other administrators in the process of examination would be more helpful in the detection of more faults & it will lead to a clear and effectual process of examination.

REFERENCES:

1. James R. Tertiary student attitudes to invigilated, online summative examinations. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* 2016; 13:19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-016-0015-0>.
2. Macht M, Haupt C, Ellgring H. The perceived function of eating is changed during examination stress: a field study. *Eating Behaviors* 2005; 6: 109-112.
3. Ivers N, Jamtvedt G, Flottorp S, Young JM, Odgaard-Jensen J, et al. Audit and feedback: effects on professional practice and healthcare outcomes. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2012; 13; 6:CD000259. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD000259.pub3
4. Hurst D. Audit and feedback had small but potentially important improvements in

- professional practice. *Evid Based Dent* 2013; 14(1):8-9.
5. Graham Copeland, Clinical Audit Development Director, *Practical Clinical Audit Handbook*, published by the Clinical Governance Support team in March 2005, P.3.
 6. Lerardi JA. Taking the 'Sting' Out of Examination Reviews: A Student-Centered Approach. *Journal of Nursing Education* 2014; 53(7): 428. <https://doi.org/10.3928/01484834-20140619-13>
 7. Sinclair HK, Cleland JA. Undergraduate Medical Students: Who Seeks Formative Feedback? *Medical Education* 2007; 41(6): 580-82.
 8. Sales AE, Schalm C, Baylon MA, Fraser KD. Data for improvement and clinical excellence: report of an interrupted time series trial of feedback in long-term care. *Implement Sci.* 2014; 11(9):161.
 9. Jonsson, A. Facilitating productive use of feedback in higher education. *Active Learning in Higher Education* 2012; 14(1): 63 - 76.
 10. Halverson, H. The Key to Great Feedback? Praise the Process, Not the Person. 99U 2014. Retrieved from:<http://99u.com/articles/19442/the-key-to-great-feedback-praise-the-process-not-the-person>.
 11. McCarthy J. Evaluating written, audio and video feedback in higher education summative assessment tasks. *Issues in Educational Research* 2015;25(2): 153-169. <http://www.iier.org.au/iier25/mccarthy.html>
 12. Poorman SG, Mastorovich ML. Using metacognitive strategies to help students learn in pretest and posttest review. *Nurse Educator* 2008; 33: 176-180.
 13. Saed AM, Abas NI. Feedback of undergraduate nursing students about the objective structured practical examination. *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice* 2017; 7(3): 68-76.
 14. Ozden MY, Erturk I, Sanli R. Students' Perceptions of Online Assessment: A Case Study. *Journal of Distance Education* 2004; 19(2): 77-92.